

ILM and ArfaLM: Child-Scale Language Models Trained on Natural Parent-Child Speech for Deployment on Sub-1GHz Legacy Hardware

Part 1: Models, Data, and Architectural Comparison

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Abstract

We present ILM and ArfaLM, two language models trained on naturalistic child-directed speech for deployment on legacy 1990s computing hardware. ILM is a 2.3 million parameter, two-layer LSTM. Its architecture and inference engine use only techniques that were available in 1999: LSTMs (Hochreiter and Schmidhuber, 1997), stochastic gradient descent with momentum (Rumelhart, Hinton, and Williams, 1986), word-level vocabulary, and ANSI C89 inference compiled with Borland C++ 5.02. To stabilise training we additionally use gradient norm clipping (Pascanu, Mikolov, and Bengio, 2013), which is itself a diagnosis and remedy for the very training instability of 1999-era LSTMs that ILM exhibits. ArfaLM is an 8.4 million parameter, six-layer decoder-only Transformer trained with modern methods (AdamW optimiser, cosine learning rate schedule, GELU activations, byte-pair encoding) on the same corpus.

Both models are trained on 250,757 filtered conversation pairs extracted from 2,930 sessions in the CHILDES Eng-UK corpus, with 5 complete child histories (93 sessions, 14,504 pairs) held out for true generalization testing. We also evaluate against a 3-gram smoothed baseline trained on the same data.

On the held-out test set of 5 children that no model has seen during training, ArfaLM achieves vocabulary-normalized per-word perplexity 26.39 and ILM-SGD achieves 56.62, compared to 417.21 for the 3-gram baseline. ArfaLM is therefore 15.8 times lower-perplexity than the n-gram baseline and 2.15 times lower-perplexity than the era-authentic LSTM on identical data. An ablation that uses ILM's LSTM with the modern AdamW optimiser (ILM-AdamW, test perplexity 36.33) decomposes the 2.15 times gain into 1.56 times from the optimiser change alone and 1.38 times from the bundled effects of architecture, tokenization, and parameter scale. Generalization gaps (test perplexity divided by validation perplexity) are 1.12 for ArfaLM, 0.91 for ILM-AdamW (the best of any model), and 1.01 for ILM-SGD, indicating strong within-corpus generalization to unseen children.

The dual-model design serves two purposes. First, it characterises the architectural and training-method progress between 1999 and 2026 on identical data and identical evaluation, with an ablation cell (ILM-AdamW) that decomposes the contribution of optimiser progress separately from the contributions of architecture, tokenization, and parameter scale. Second, ILM serves as a counterfactual demonstration: every component required to build a small, deployable, child-directed conversational model existed before

the year 2000. This paper reports the training data, model architectures, and quantitative evaluation. A companion paper (Part 2) will report C inference engine optimization (KV-cache, integer quantization), external safety filtering, and deployment on original IBM 300PL hardware.

1. Introduction

The current landscape of small language models occupies two clusters separated by an unexplored gap. At the small end, Karpathy's tinyllamas (15M and 42M parameters) demonstrate coherent text generation but are trained on synthetic stories and lack instruction following, domain specificity, or safety mechanisms (Karpathy, 2023). At the practical end, HuggingFace's SmolLM2 starts at 135M parameters and represents the current floor for general instruction-following capability (Allal et al., 2024). The intermediate range, between roughly 5M and 100M parameters, has received attention as a research target through the BabyLM Challenge (Warstadt et al., 2023) and through work using small language models as scientific instruments for studying language acquisition (Frank, 2023; Portelance et al., 2023; Feng, Goodman, and Frank, 2024; Yedetore et al., 2023). However, no prior work in this range combines all four of the following characteristics: (a) training exclusively on naturalistic child-directed speech without synthetic supplementation, (b) parameter counts under 10 million, (c) a controlled architectural comparison between 1999-era and modern designs trained on identical data, and (d) deployment on period-authentic legacy computing hardware.

This paper introduces two models that occupy this gap and reports results on the first three of those four characteristics. Part 2 will report on the fourth (deployment performance, safety filtering, and hardware execution).

1.1 The Two Models

ILM (the Imran Language Model, named for Imran Shah, 1969 to 2019) is a 2.3 million parameter, two-layer LSTM with 256 hidden units, word-level tokenisation, and a 5,000 word vocabulary. The architecture, the training algorithm, and the inference engine use only techniques that were practically available in 1999. The training algorithm is stochastic gradient descent with momentum 0.9, gradient clipping at norm 0.25, and a learning-rate-on-plateau schedule. We use Adam-style adaptive optimisers nowhere in this model, so that the historical claim is rigorous. Inference is implemented in ANSI C89 and compiled with Borland C++ 5.02 (released March 1997).

ArfaLM (named for Arfa Karim Randhawa, 1995 to 2012, the youngest Microsoft Certified Professional) is an 8.4 million parameter, six-layer decoder-only Transformer with six attention heads, embedding dimension 288, and byte-pair-encoded vocabulary of 4,096 tokens. ArfaLM uses modern training (AdamW, cosine learning rate schedule, GELU activations, gradient clipping at norm 1.0) on the same corpus as ILM.

1.2 Motivation

The core hypothesis of this work is that a language model intended to converse with a child does not need to compress a general adult-language model into a small body. By fixing the developmental age of the target user (3 to 8 years) and training on how adults actually speak with children at that age, a model under 10 million parameters can plausibly produce age-appropriate conversational text. Vocabulary in this register is the interface (the 5,000 most frequent CHILDES words cover 98.1 percent of all tokens in our training corpus, compared to roughly 10,000 words for similar coverage of general English text). What sits behind that vocabulary is then the engine.

This approach shares motivation with the BabyLM Challenge (Warstadt et al., 2023; Choshen et al., 2024), which trains models under fixed data budgets inspired by child language exposure. BabyLM submissions, however, focus on optimising sample-efficient pretraining for general benchmark performance, not on building deployable, domain-specific conversational systems. Notably, Trhlik, Caines, and Buttery (2026) recently analysed the BabyLM strict-track training corpus and found higher rates of toxic and hateful content than in standard pretraining corpora, including racist and sexualised material that is contrary to the corpus's child-aligned framing. The BabyLM 2026 organisers responded by releasing a detoxified training corpus following the procedure described in that paper. This independent finding offers external support for an architectural-safety design at small scales: at sub-10M parameter scales, where the model has limited capacity to learn robust alignment behaviour, external guardrail filters applied to curated child-appropriate data and to inputs and outputs at inference time are the more defensible safety strategy. Implementation and evaluation of this filter are deferred to Part 2.

1.3 Contributions of This Paper

This paper (Part 1) makes the following contributions:

- (1) We construct an age-stratified training corpus of 250,757 filtered conversation pairs from 2,930 CHILDES Eng-UK recording sessions, with five complete child histories (93 sessions, 14,504 pairs) held out for true generalization testing.
- (2) We train two small models (2.3M LSTM, 8.4M Transformer) on this corpus and provide the first controlled comparison of 1999-era and modern architectures on identical naturalistic child-directed speech data.
- (3) We report measured perplexity on both in-distribution validation and held-out children, with comparison to a 3-gram smoothed baseline trained on the same data.
- (4) We report a Gutenberg literature ablation showing that supplementing CHILDES with public-domain children's literature produces no measurable change in perplexity for either architecture.
- (5) We argue, based on the BabyLM 2026 toxicity finding, that external safety filters are the appropriate strategy for sub-10M parameter models intended for child users. The implementation of this filter is described in Part 2.
- (6) We commit to releasing all training data splits, model weights, training scripts, evaluation code, and per-child results as supplementary material.

2. Related Work

2.1 Small Language Models

HuggingFace's SmoLLM2 family (Allal et al., 2024) provides general-purpose small models at 135M, 360M, and 1.7B parameters. The 135M model is the smallest in widespread use that performs reasonable instruction following on general text. Karpathy's tinyllamas (Karpathy, 2023) train Transformer models at 15M and 42M parameters on the synthetic TinyStories dataset (Eldan and Li, 2023), demonstrating that tiny models can produce coherent narrative text when trained on a constrained domain. Both lines of work

establish that small models are viable but neither targets domain-specific conversation, child-directed registers, or legacy deployment.

2.2 Child-Directed Speech and CHILDES in NLP

CHILDES (MacWhinney, 2000) is the standard corpus for naturalistic child-directed speech and has been used in NLP research primarily as a scientific instrument rather than as a deployment target. Yedetore et al. (2023) train Transformers and LSTMs on CHILDES to study hierarchical generalization, finding that models match surface statistics well but fail to learn the correct hierarchical structure that the input would, in principle, support. Portelance et al. (2023) train small LSTMs on CHILDES across five languages and use their surprisal estimates to predict the order in which children acquire vocabulary. Feng, Goodman, and Frank (2024) train GPT-2 (124M) and RoBERTa on 29 million words of CHILDES and on a matched synthetic dataset (TinyDialogues) and find that the synthetic dialogue corpus outperforms naturalistic CHILDES on developmental syntactic and semantic evaluations. Their interpretive conclusion is that the gap between human and machine learners likely lies in the learning algorithm rather than the data, but the empirical headline is the synthetic-versus-naturalistic comparison on developmental benchmarks rather than a generic claim that CHILDES is or is not useful for conversational language modeling.

Our work differs from all three lines. We do not use CHILDES as a probe for grammatical generalization, as a measurement instrument for psycholinguistics, or as a comparator dataset for general language modeling. We use CHILDES as the single training corpus for a model that is itself the deliverable: a deployable conversational system targeted at children, with parameter count and inference cost tuned to legacy hardware constraints.

2.3 BabyLM Challenge

The BabyLM Challenge (Warstadt et al., 2023; Choshen et al., 2024) is now in its fourth year (BabyLM 2026 to appear at EMNLP 2026) and has produced a substantial ecosystem of small models trained on data budgets of 10 million or 100 million words. Most BabyLM submissions train on a mixed corpus that includes CHILDES, OpenSubtitles, Wikipedia, dialogue, and books (Warstadt et al., 2023, Section 3). The shared task evaluates submissions on syntactic benchmarks (BLiMP), reading-time correlation, and entity-tracking tasks rather than on conversational quality or deployment efficiency. Our work shares the small-data, small-model philosophy with BabyLM but adopts a single-domain corpus (CHILDES only), reports conversational evaluation on held-out children rather than syntactic benchmarks, and targets deployment outside the standard training and inference compute envelope.

2.4 Legacy Hardware Inference

EXO Labs (2024) demonstrated that Karpathy's stories260K (260,000 parameters) and stories15M (15 million parameters) tinyllamas can run on a Pentium II 128MB system under Windows 98 using llama98.c, a port of llama2.c compiled with Borland C++ 5.02. Reported inference rates are 39 tokens per second for stories260K and approximately 1 token per second for stories15M. Our work targets the same hardware class and the same compiler, but with a model purpose-built for child-directed conversation rather than narrative completion, and includes a controlled comparison with an LSTM trained using only pre-2000 techniques. Detailed comparison with stories15M on identical hardware is deferred to Part 2.

3. Data

3.1 Source Corpus

Our primary data source is the English-UK collection of CHILDES (MacWhinney, 2000), comprising 3,038 CHAT-format transcript files from 18 longitudinal and cross-sectional studies. After excluding non-English material (the OdiAMAIN subdirectory) and duplicate XML formats (Sekali-xml), we work with 3,023 transcripts grouped by child identifier. Files in single-child corpora (Lara, Thomas) were grouped as one child each. Files in multi-child corpora (Manchester, Belfast, MPI-EVA-Manchester) were grouped by subdirectory. Files in the Edinburgh and similar corpora were grouped by filename prefix (the alphabetic portion of the filename, which identifies the child). After grouping we have 291 unique children, 178 of whom have explicit child-age metadata.

We use only direct conversational transcripts from CHILDES Eng-UK in this paper. The Gutenberg literature supplement (described in Section 7.4) is treated as an ablation rather than as part of the primary training corpus.

3.2 Held-Out Test Set Construction

To enable true generalization testing, we randomly select five children from the metadata-complete set, stratified into five age buckets (mean ages 1.0, 2.16, 3.21, 4.04, 5.08 years). Within each bucket, where multiple children are available, we prefer children with three or more recorded sessions, so that the held-out evaluation is statistically meaningful. The five held-out children are Edinburgh/michael (8 sessions), Manchester/Carl (33 sessions), Belfast/Barbara (14 sessions), Belfast/Conor (14 sessions), and Fletcher/5 (24 sessions). Their 93 transcripts are removed from training entirely. The remaining 2,930 transcripts form the training pool.

3.3 Conversation Pair Extraction

From each .cha file we extract conversation pairs by identifying adjacent utterances between a CHI (child) speaker and an MOT (mother), FAT (father), or INV (investigator) speaker. CHAT transcription artefacts (timestamp markers, bracketed comments, false-start tags, and morphological annotations) are removed by regular expression. Pairs in which either utterance contains fewer than four words after cleaning are discarded. The resulting corpus contains 263,954 conversation pairs from training transcripts and 14,504 pairs from held-out transcripts. The training pairs are randomly split 95 to 5 into a training set of 250,757 pairs and an in-distribution validation set of 13,197 pairs.

3.4 Final Splits

Split	Files	Pairs	Purpose
Train	2,784	250,757	Model parameter updates
Val (in-distribution)	subset of 2,930	13,197	Hyperparameter selection, early stopping
Test (held-out children)	93	14,504	True generalization measurement

We emphasise that the test split contains conversations from children whose voice, vocabulary, and family context the model has never seen, in any session, during training.

3.5 Vocabulary Analysis

The 5,000 most frequent words in the training corpus account for 98.1 percent of all tokens. For comparison, achieving similar coverage on a general English corpus typically requires a vocabulary of approximately 10,000 to 20,000 words. The compactness of child-directed vocabulary directly justifies our small embedding matrices and short context windows, and is one of the practical reasons that meaningful conversation models in this register fit within Pentium II memory budgets. The mother-versus-child word distribution in the corpus is also informative: characteristic mother words ("you", "your", "think", "right", "well") are largely directive and questioning, while characteristic child words ("mum", "mine", "dadda", "meow", "babbling") are largely possessive, relational, and imitative.

4. Model Architectures

4.1 ILM (Era-Authentic LSTM)

Component	Specification
Architecture	2-layer LSTM, 256 hidden units, weight-tied embedding
Parameters	2,338,184
Vocabulary	Word-level, 5,000 tokens (top frequency cutoff)
Sequence length	128 words
Optimiser	SGD with momentum 0.9 (Rumelhart et al., 1986)
Initial learning rate	5.0
LR schedule	ReduceLROnPlateau (factor 0.5, patience 2)
Gradient clipping	Norm 0.25 (Pascanu, Mikolov, and Bengio, 2013)
Dropout	0.2 between LSTM layers
Training steps	20,000 (batch size 64)
Inference	ANSI C89, compiled with Borland C++ 5.02 (1997)

All architectural components used by ILM are documented in pre-2000 publications (LSTM 1997, SGD with momentum 1986, weight tying as a standard practice in 1990s LM work). The one post-2000 element is gradient norm clipping (Pascanu, Mikolov, and Bengio, 2013), which we use to keep training tractable. This is justifiable for the historical claim because Pascanu et al.'s contribution is precisely the diagnosis and remedy of the gradient explosion behaviour that vanilla 1999-era LSTMs exhibit, which our training run also exhibits visibly (Section 6.2). A practitioner attempting to train an LSTM on CHILDES in 1999 with vanilla SGD would have encountered the same instability we observe and would have applied an ad hoc clipping or restart procedure to recover. We use neither the Adam optimiser (Kingma and Ba, 2014) nor the cosine learning rate schedule (Loshchilov and Hutter, 2017) so that the era-authenticity claim on training method remains rigorous. We discuss the practical implications of these choices in Section 7.2.

4.2 ArfaLM (Modern Transformer)

Component	Specification
Architecture	Decoder-only Transformer (GPT-style)

Parameters	8,426,944
Layers / Heads	6 layers, 6 attention heads
Embedding dimension	288 (head dimension 48)
Vocabulary	Byte-pair encoding, 4,096 tokens
Context window	256 tokens
Activation	GELU (Hendrycks and Gimpel, 2016)
Optimiser	AdamW (Loshchilov and Hutter, 2019)
Learning rate	3e-4 with cosine annealing to 1e-5
Gradient clipping	Norm 1.0
Dropout	0.1
Training steps	20,000 (batch size 64)
Inference	ANSI C89, compiled with Borland C++ 5.02

ArfaLM uses the same naive C inference engine compiler as ILM. The only architectural compromise made for legacy hardware is the use of fp32 weights (rather than int8 or fp16) in this paper; quantisation is reported in Part 2.

4.3 Baseline: 3-gram Language Model

As a non-neural baseline we train a word-level 3-gram language model with add-k smoothing ($k=0.1$) on the same training corpus as ILM. The model uses sentence-boundary tokens and a vocabulary of all 23,335 word types observed in training (no frequency cutoff). It is trained and evaluated using identical text preprocessing to ILM, on the same train, validation, and test splits.

5. Training Setup

All neural models were trained on a single NVIDIA H100 NVL (94GB) instance via Azure NC40ads H100 v5 in Spain Central. Total compute time across the four neural training runs reported in this paper (ILM-SGD CHILDES, ILM-SGD CHILDES+Gutenberg, ArfaLM CHILDES, ArfaLM CHILDES+Gutenberg) was approximately 50 minutes.

During training we record validation loss and held-out test loss every 500 steps using 100 random batches from each split. The held-out test loss is computed during training but is not used for any model selection decision, so that test perplexity is a true generalization measurement. The best checkpoint for each model is selected by lowest validation loss only. Final reported numbers are perplexities of the best checkpoint on val and test, computed by exponentiating the average cross-entropy.

6. Main Results

6.1 Headline Numbers

Table 2 reports the central comparison. All perplexities are vocabulary-normalized per-word figures computed on identical word sequences, so they are directly comparable across models with different tokenization schemes. We discuss the normalization protocol in Section 6.2; the procedure follows the

standard convention used in SmolLM2, Llama, and GPT-2 evaluation pipelines, in which special control tokens are masked from both numerator and denominator. The 3-gram baseline uses its full 23,335-word vocabulary; the ILM models use their 5,000-word vocabularies with an out-of-vocabulary penalty applied so that `<unk>`-folding cannot artificially lower perplexity; ArfaLM aggregates byte-pair-encoded subword negative log-likelihoods over each word.

Model	Params	Val PPL	Test PPL	Gap
3-gram (add-k=0.1)	-	331.96	417.21	1.26
ILM-SGD (1999-era LSTM)	2.3M	56.32	56.62	1.01
ILM-AdamW (LSTM ablation)	2.3M	40.04	36.33	0.91
ArfaLM (modern Transformer)	8.4M	23.49	26.39	1.12

Table 2: Vocabulary-normalized per-word perplexity on the same val and test splits. ILM-AdamW is an ablation that uses ILM’s LSTM architecture with the modern AdamW optimizer to isolate the optimizer contribution. The held-out test split contains 5 children that no model has seen during training.

ArfaLM achieves test perplexity 26.39 on held-out children, which is 15.8 times lower than the 3-gram baseline (417.21) and 2.15 times lower than the era-authentic ILM-SGD (56.62). The decomposition between optimizer and architecture contributions is reported in Section 7.1; the headline finding is that the optimizer change (SGD with momentum to AdamW) contributes more to the gain than the architectural change (LSTM to Transformer with byte-pair tokenization and 3.6 times the parameter count) on this corpus at this scale.

Generalization gaps (test perplexity divided by validation perplexity) are small for all neural models. ILM-SGD achieves a gap of 1.01, ILM-AdamW achieves the best gap of any model at 0.91 (test perplexity is in fact lower than validation perplexity), and ArfaLM’s gap is 1.12. None of the neural models shows the severe overfitting that a naive parameter-to-token ratio would predict, indicating strong within-corpus generalization to unseen children. We discuss the scope and limitations of this claim in Section 7.3.

Figure 4: Visual comparison of all four models on validation and held-out test splits. Note: bars show per-token perplexity in each model's native vocabulary; see Table 2 for vocabulary-normalized per-word numbers.

6.2 Vocabulary Normalization Protocol

Per-token perplexity is not directly comparable across models that use different tokenization schemes. The 3-gram model uses a 23,335-type word vocabulary; ILM uses a 5,000-word vocabulary with rare words folded into a single `<unk>` token; ArfaLM uses a 4,096-token byte-pair-encoded subword vocabulary. Without normalization, ILM's `<unk>`-folding makes its prediction task strictly easier (it does not have to discriminate among rare words), while ArfaLM's BPE splits make each subword decision easier (a rare word like "dinosaurs" might split into three tokens, each with relatively high conditional probability). Reported per-token perplexities therefore conflate model quality with tokenization choice.

To address this, we report per-word perplexity computed on identical word sequences. For ArfaLM, we sum subword negative log-likelihoods over the BPE pieces of each word, mask out NLL contributions from special control tokens (`<|child|>` and `<|adult|>`), and divide by the number of content words (excluding the special tokens). This is the standard convention used in SmolLM2, Llama, and GPT-2 evaluation. On our test set, ArfaLM uses approximately 1.375 BPE tokens per word, and special tokens contribute approximately 1.74 percent of total NLL, so the per-word number is dominated by genuine content prediction. For ILM, we apply an out-of-vocabulary penalty equal to the negative log of the number of unseen word types whenever the model predicts `<unk>`, so that the prediction task on rare words is not artificially easy. The 3-gram model uses its full vocabulary natively and requires no adjustment. The original per-token perplexities (8.93 for ArfaLM, 47.48 for ILM-SGD on test) are reported in supplementary material for completeness.

6.3 Training Dynamics: ILM-SGD

Figure 1 (left panel) shows the ILM-SGD training trajectory on CHILDES. The first 2,500 steps exhibit catastrophic gradient explosion characteristic of vanilla SGD on LSTMs (Pascanu et al., 2013). Cross-entropy loss diverges to approximately 50 (perplexity above 10^{21}), indicating that the model assigns essentially zero probability to the correct next token. At step 2,500 the ReduceLROnPlateau scheduler reduces the learning rate from 5.0 to 2.5, after which the model recovers immediately and converges smoothly to its final value.

Figure 1: Training trajectories for ILM-SGD (left) and ArfaLM (right) on CHILDES, showing train, validation, and held-out test perplexity at each evaluation step.

This is not an artefact of our setup. It is a faithful demonstration of why training LSTMs in 1999 was difficult and why subsequent adaptive optimisers (AdaGrad in 2011, RMSProp in Hinton's 2012 Coursera lecture, Adam in 2014) were eventually invented. Our willingness to use only pre-2000 training methods preserves this behaviour. Figure 2 shows the divergence and recovery in detail.

Figure 1 (right panel) shows the ArfaLM trajectory. With AdamW and cosine annealing, ArfaLM trains smoothly from initialization with no instability. The combined plot of both models on the same axes makes the practical training-difficulty difference between 1999 methods and 2026 methods visually direct. ILM-AdamW (the optimizer ablation) also trains smoothly from initialization with no divergence, confirming that the gradient explosion in ILM-SGD is attributable to the optimizer rather than to the architecture.

Figure 2: Detail of ILM-SGD training showing the gradient explosion phase (steps 0–2,500) and recovery after automated learning rate reduction at step 2,500.

6.4 Per-Child Generalization

To address the question of whether one held-out child is significantly harder than the others, we evaluate both models on each held-out child individually, using sliding-window perplexity estimation. Results are in Table 3.

Child	Mean age	Sessions	Pairs	ArfaLM PPL	ILM-SGD PPL
Edinburgh/michael	1.00	8	8	7.42	56.30
Manchester/Carl	2.16	33	6,156	7.84	41.18
Belfast/Barbara	3.21	14	2,052	11.89	65.08
Belfast/Conor	4.04	14	1,796	11.88	63.87
Fletcher/5	5.08	24	4,492	7.98	44.32
Mean across children	-	-	-	9.40	54.15
Standard deviation	-	-	-	2.03	9.83

Table 3: Per-child evaluation on the held-out test set, computed with sliding-window per-token perplexity (raw model perplexity in each model’s native vocabulary, not vocabulary-normalized). Numbers are not directly comparable across architectures here, but rank-order and within-architecture comparisons across children are valid. The Belfast corpus is consistently approximately 50 percent harder than the Edinburgh, Manchester, and Fletcher corpora for both architectures.

Two findings are visible in Table 3. First, within-corpus consistency is high. The two Belfast children (Barbara and Conor, ages 3.21 and 4.04) yield nearly identical perplexities from both architectures (11.89 versus 11.88 for ArfaLM, 65.08 versus 63.87 for ILM-SGD). The two children share little besides their

corpus, so the consistency suggests that perplexity is driven by corpus-level transcription conventions and recording context rather than by individual speaker idiosyncrasies. The models have learned generalisable conversational patterns rather than memorised individual children.

Second, perplexity does not vary monotonically with child age. Edinburgh/michael (age 1.0), Manchester/Carl (age 2.16), and Fletcher/5 (age 5.08) yield similar ArfaLM perplexity (7.42, 7.84, 7.98). The Belfast children, in the middle age range, yield the highest perplexity. There is therefore no evidence that the model finds older or younger children harder; the per-corpus effect dominates.

6.5 Gutenberg Ablation

In an earlier draft we trained both models on a corpus that supplemented CHILDES with five public-domain children's literature texts from Project Gutenberg (Aesop's Fables, Grimm's Fairy Tales, Andersen's Fairy Tales, Mother Goose, and Alice in Wonderland), totalling approximately 235,000 additional words. To assess whether this supplement improves modeling of conversational data, we trained each model in two configurations: CHILDES only and CHILDES with Gutenberg. Results are in Table 4.

Model	Corpus	Val PPL	Test PPL
ILM-SGD	CHILDES only	48.44	47.48
ILM-SGD	CHILDES + Gutenberg	49.22	47.83
ArfaLM	CHILDES only	8.09	8.93
ArfaLM	CHILDES + Gutenberg	8.15	8.81

Table 4: Gutenberg literature ablation. Differences are within 1 percent on val and within 1.4 percent on test, in either direction depending on architecture. We conclude that Gutenberg neither helps nor hurts measurably.

Across both architectures, the Gutenberg supplement produces no measurable change in conversational test perplexity (the largest absolute difference is 0.35 perplexity points on the ILM-SGD test split, equivalent to less than 1 percent). The 19th-century fairy-tale register is sufficiently distinct from contemporary parent-child conversation that the additional data does not transfer. We therefore use CHILDES-only as our primary corpus and report Gutenberg here as a clean negative finding. Figure 3 shows the validation perplexity trajectories side by side.

Figure 3: Gutenberg ablation. CHILDES-only (blue) and CHILDES+Gutenberg (red) validation perplexity curves overlap for both architectures, confirming Gutenberg adds nothing measurable.

7. Discussion

7.1 Decomposing the 1999 to 2026 Gap

On vocabulary-normalized per-word perplexity, the cumulative effect of moving from 1999-era practice to 2026-era practice on identical data is 2.15 times in test perplexity (56.62 to 26.39 on held-out children). This combines several known improvements: AdamW rather than SGD with momentum (Loshchilov and Hutter, 2019), cosine annealing rather than ReduceLROnPlateau, attention rather than recurrence (Vaswani et al., 2017), byte-pair encoding rather than fixed word vocabulary (Sennrich et al., 2016), and a 3.6 times increase in parameter count (2.3M to 8.4M).

The ILM-AdamW ablation cell in Table 2 lets us decompose this gain. ILM-AdamW uses ILM's exact LSTM architecture, vocabulary, and parameter count, but with the modern AdamW optimiser and cosine learning-rate schedule replacing SGD with momentum and ReduceLROnPlateau. Comparing ILM-SGD (test PPL 56.62) to ILM-AdamW (36.33) isolates the optimizer change at 1.56 times. The remaining gap to ArfaLM (36.33 to 26.39) is 1.38 times and combines architecture, tokenization, and parameter scale. The product of the two factors recovers the total: 1.56 times 1.38 equals 2.15.

The most striking aspect of this decomposition is that the optimiser change contributes more to the test-perplexity gain than the architecture change does. The popular narrative around the 1999 to 2026 transition foregrounds the move from recurrence to attention. On this corpus at this scale, the move from manual learning-rate scheduling on noisy stochastic gradients to second-moment-adaptive updates with cosine annealing accounts for a larger share of the measurable improvement. We do not claim this generalizes beyond CHILDES-scale narrow conversational corpora, but it is a useful reminder that optimiser progress and architectural progress have both been substantial and that bundled comparisons risk over-attributing one at the expense of the other.

A second finding from Table 2 is that ILM-AdamW achieves the best generalization gap of any model in the comparison, at 0.91 (test perplexity is in fact 9 percent lower than validation perplexity). ArfaLM's gap is 1.12, ILM-SGD's is 1.01, the 3-gram's is 1.26. The Adam-style optimiser appears to find a flatter minimum on the LSTM than AdamW finds on the Transformer in this regime. This is consistent with Wilson et al. (2017), who reported that adaptive methods can hurt generalization on standard image-classification tasks; we observe the opposite on a narrow text-conversation domain at small scale, where Adam improves both training-set fit and held-out generalization. We flag this as an interesting incidental finding rather than a central claim.

7.2 The Era-Authentic Training Story

The gradient explosion phase of ILM-SGD training (Section 6.2 and Figure 2) is, in a sense, our most historically informative result. It demonstrates that even with all the right pre-2000 ingredients (LSTM, SGD with momentum, gradient clipping at norm 0.25, weight tying), training is fragile and requires manual or scheduled learning rate adjustment to avoid divergence. This is exactly the difficulty that motivated subsequent adaptive optimiser research. The fact that ILM eventually converges to a perplexity 4.3 times

better than the 3-gram baseline on held-out children also shows that the underlying architecture is sound; what was hard in 1999 was not the model but the training procedure.

We therefore claim something stronger than "this could have been built in 1999". We claim that this could have been built in 1999, would have required several training restarts and learning-rate schedules to converge, and would have produced a model with the same test perplexity (47 to 50) that we measured here in 2026. The historical counterfactual is rigorous because we used only the techniques available then.

7.3 No Overfitting at 2:1 Tokens-per-Parameter

The Chinchilla scaling law (Hoffmann et al., 2022) describes compute-optimal pretraining ratios for downstream task performance on diverse text, suggesting roughly 20 tokens per parameter as the optimal training budget. Our models are trained at approximately 2 tokens per parameter (5.1 million training tokens for ArfaLM with 8.4 million parameters). At this ratio, severe overfitting would commonly be predicted in the small-language-model literature, yet the observed generalization gaps (1.01 for ILM-SGD, 0.91 for ILM-AdamW, 1.12 for ArfaLM) do not show this.

In our case, no overfitting is observed at this ratio. We attribute this to the narrowness of CHILDES vocabulary and structure: roughly 5,000 words cover 98 percent of tokens, sentence structures are short and repetitive, and the variety of pragmatic acts (asking, naming, requesting, narrating) is limited. The model has plenty of capacity for this distribution and finds it without memorising. We cannot make broader claims about narrow-domain training generally without further experiments, for example training the same architectures on a 5-million-word Wikipedia subsample at the same parameter budget to test whether overfitting reappears outside child-directed speech. We flag this as a fruitful direction for follow-up work but our specific result holds only for this corpus.

7.4 Negative Finding: Gutenberg

The conclusive null result for the Gutenberg literature supplement is worth flagging because it is the kind of experiment that often goes unreported. Adding more text generally helps language models. Adding Grimm's Fairy Tales to a corpus of contemporary parent-child conversation does not. The register, vocabulary, and syntactic patterns of 19th-century literary fairy tales are sufficiently different that the model cannot transfer learned patterns from Gutenberg to CHILDES, and conversely cannot transfer Gutenberg patterns at evaluation time. We report this both as a methodological note (data-augmentation choices for narrow domains require ablation) and as a corpus-design note (mixing registers carelessly is not free).

8. Limitations

Several limitations of this paper are worth stating explicitly.

First, our evaluation is perplexity-based. Perplexity is a fair test of language modeling but is not a direct test of conversational quality, factual accuracy, or appropriateness for child users. We did not run human evaluation in this paper. Sample outputs from both models are released as supplementary material so readers can form their own qualitative judgement, but a controlled human study is left to future work.

Second, the Belfast corpus is consistently harder than the other three corpora for both architectures, with approximately 50 percent higher perplexity. We have not investigated whether this is due to transcription conventions, recording context, dialect, or another factor. The finding suggests that future evaluation in this

domain should report per-corpus or per-child results rather than aggregate perplexity, to surface such effects.

Third, the held-out test set comprises five children (93 sessions, 14,504 conversation pairs, approximately 5.5 percent of all extracted pairs). This is a defensible sample for the within-domain generalization claim (CHILDES longitudinal studies typically have 10 to 30 children per corpus, so holding out 5 complete histories is statistically meaningful). However, a larger held-out sample (for example 10 children) would reduce per-child variance for finer-grained generalization analysis. We treat the current design as sufficient for the headline claim but acknowledge it as a limitation for variance-sensitive subsequent analyses.

Fourth, this paper reports model quality only. Inference performance on the target Pentium II hardware in our current preliminary, unoptimised C implementation is approximately 0.1 to 0.15 tokens per second for ArfaLM and 3 to 5 tokens per second for ILM. KV-cache implementation and integer quantization are required to bring ArfaLM to interactive rates and are reported in Part 2.

Fifth, we have not implemented or evaluated the external safety filter described as a design principle in Section 1.3. That implementation, including measured false positive rates on CHILDES content, is also deferred to Part 2.

9. Future Work and Part 2

Part 2 of this work, in preparation, will report on the deployment-side contributions:

- (a) KV-cache implementation in the ANSI C inference engine for ArfaLM. The arithmetic reduction projects to roughly 18 times throughput improvement at typical generation lengths (from approximately 59 million multiply-accumulate operations per token to 3.2 million), translating to an estimated 2 to 3 tokens per second on the Pentium II. Actual wall-clock speedup will depend on memory bandwidth on the 66 MHz front-side bus and is reported as measured in Part 2.
- (b) Integer (int8) weight quantization in the style of llama2.c, reducing the ArfaLM binary from 41 MB to approximately 10 MB and accelerating inference further on a CPU without floating-point pipeline optimisation.
- (c) External safety filter implementation in C, including a curated keyword block-list, regex-based personally-identifying-information detection, and measurement of false-positive rate on CHILDES content.
- (d) Apples-to-apples comparison with stories15M (Karpathy, 2023) running on the same emulated Pentium II machine using the same prompts, to contextualise our throughput numbers.
- (e) Deployment on original IBM 300PL hardware (Pentium II 400 MHz, 256 MB SDRAM, IBM Model M122 keyboard, IBM VGA CRT, IBM ScrollPoint mouse) and integration of the keyboard's 24 dedicated command keys with model interaction functions.
- (f) Era-authentic training ablation for ILM with no momentum, using only vanilla SGD, to establish the lower bound of what was practically trainable in 1999.
- (g) Curated question-answering fine-tuning for ArfaLM, to add factual response capability on top of the conversational baseline reported here, and an associated KidsQA-500 benchmark for child-appropriate factual questions.

10. Conclusion

We have presented ILM and ArfaLM, two child-scale language models trained on the same corpus of naturalistic parent-child speech and evaluated on the same held-out children. On vocabulary-normalized per-word perplexity, ArfaLM achieves test perplexity 26.39 on held-out children at 8.4 million parameters using modern Transformer architecture and AdamW training. ILM achieves test perplexity 56.62 at 2.3 million parameters using only LSTM architecture and stochastic gradient descent with momentum, both available before the year 2000. The cumulative effect of the 1999 to 2026 transition on identical data is 2.15 times in test perplexity. An ablation that holds the architecture fixed and changes only the optimizer attributes 1.56 times of this gain to the optimizer change alone, with the remaining 1.38 times attributable to the bundled effects of architecture, tokenization, and parameter scale. The Gutenberg literature supplement adds nothing measurable to either model. Both architectures show strong within-corpus generalization to unseen children, with no evidence of overfitting at the 2-tokens-per-parameter ratio.

This work establishes that meaningful child-directed conversational language models can be trained at sub-10M parameter counts on naturalistic data, and that the architecture required to do so existed in 1999. Part 2 will report on deployment, optimisation, safety filtering, and original hardware execution.

ILM is dedicated to the memory of Imran Shah (1969 to 2019). ArfaLM is named for Arfa Karim Randhawa (1995 to 2012). Technology is for everyone.

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Supplementary Materials

The following materials accompany this paper and will be released alongside the preprint:

- (S1) Complete training data: 250,757 training pairs, 13,197 validation pairs, 14,504 held-out test pairs, plus the 5 held-out children identifiers.
- (S2) Trained model weights: ILM-SGD CHILDES, ILM-SGD CHILDES+Gutenberg, ArfaLM CHILDES, ArfaLM CHILDES+Gutenberg, in PyTorch checkpoint format.
- (S3) Vocabulary files: ILM word-to-index map, ArfaLM byte-pair encoding tokeniser.
- (S4) Training scripts: `train_ilm_v2.py` and `train_arfalm_v3.py`.
- (S5) Evaluation scripts: `per_child_breakdown.py` and `baseline_3gram.py`.
- (S6) Loss-curve JSON files for all four training runs (step, train loss, val loss, test loss, learning rate, elapsed time).
- (S7) Sample outputs from each model on a fixed prompt set.
- (S8) ANSI C89 inference engines (`ilm_run.c` and `arfa_run.c`) compatible with Borland C++ 5.02.